

CORRECTION

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Correction to: Development and validation of a framework for the assessment of school curricula on the presence of evolutionary concepts (FACE)

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In this article (Sá-Pinto et al. 2021) the statement in the Funding information section was incorrectly given as “This paper is a result of a collaborative work of researchers participating in the EuroScitizen CA17127, European Funded project (Working Group 2)” and should have read “This article/publication is based upon work from COST Action EuroScitizen (CA17127; Working Group 2), supported by COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology; www.cost.eu)”

The original article has been corrected.

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